

THERMOMECHANICAL CHARACTERISATION
OF FIBRE FINISH

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ABSTRACT

Satisfactory quality assurance of finish on fibres for production of composites still presents great difficulties. Processing industry mainly applies two methods for quality control of fibre finish: IR spectroscopy and HPLC. To perform these procedures the finish has to be detached from the fibres. Thus, insoluble components cannot be included, material changes cannot be precluded. And besides this, these methods do not provide sufficient information on the viscosity of the finish and its temperature dependency.

On the basis of the TBA an attempt was made to qualitatively determine the viscosity-temperature course of finish on fibre by means of thermo-mechanical methods. The study has proved that in spite of the minute mass portion of the finish of .5 to 2.4 per cent this can be successfully done. Thus the temperatures at glass transitions and at the beginning of the chemical reaction of the materials tested can be determined and give proof of the suitability of thermomechanical methods for characterising of finish on ready-for-processing fibres.

METHODS OF TESTING FIBRE FINISH

For the quality assurance of fibre finish processing industry employs mainly two methods: IR spectroscopy and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Accelerated mechanical tests carried out on the laminate such as measuring interlaminar shear strength are of course also suitable. The latter method, however, does not allow discrimination between the influences of the finish attached to the fibre and the matrix material itself.

For the above listed analytic methods the finish must be detached from the fibre. This requires that the solvent used and the dissolving conditions are suitable for the test method used. In the solvents used and under the conditions selected insoluble components will not be detected by these analytic methods. Furthermore, material changes (e.g. due to chemical reaction) occurring during the dissolving process cannot be precluded, and the above methods do not provide sufficient information on the viscosity of the finishes and their dependence on temperature.

Thus the question arises as to whether other methods would not be more suitable for quality control purposes. The Torsion-Braid Analysis (TBA) generally allows the determination of the viscosity-temperature course of resin systems on a carrier material, e.g. glass fibre (1 - 3). However, the quantities of resin required are much higher than the amount of finish on the ready-for-processing fibres. The mass content of finish on the samples tested lies between .5 and 2.4 per cent.

The objective of this study was to find out if the viscosity-temperature course of finish on ready-for-processing fibres could be determined by thermomechanical methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Because of their simplicity of performance and low equipment requirement already known testing methods based on the principle of free vibration and/or resonance vibration were selected, i.e. the torsion pendulum test (TPT) and the dynamic-mechanic analysis (DMA). Both methods have been adequately described in test standards and numerous publications (4 thru 6).

Preliminary tests have revealed that the method of preparing samples is of utmost importance; it plays a dominant role in the applicability of procedures and the reproducibility of test results. Samples consisted of a bundle of fibre strands (Figure 1) approx. 60 mm long for the TPT and 18 mm for the DMA. These bundles were mounted so that the strands ran as parallel as possible. Repeated lacing of the sample with wire and wrapping the ends with aluminium foil proved to be useful for the reproducibility of the TPT. A more trouble-free course of the TPT was achieved by embedding a metal strip into the centre of the fibre bundle. Both methods used a heating rate of 3 K/min. As prescribed by the two methods the environment medium used for the TPT was air and that for the

DMA was nitrogen. Both carbon and glass fibres with different finish materials were tested (Table 1).

Figure 1. Samples with jaws used for torsion pendulum tests (left) and dynamic-mechanical analysis (right) (7)

TABLE 1
Composition of studied materials (7)

Material	Type of Fibre	Type of Finish ¹⁾	Portion of Finish (Mass - %) ²⁾
1	glass	poly (vinyl acetate)	0.7
2	glass	poly (vinyl acetate)	0.6
3	glass	epoxide resin on bisphenol A base + ester	0.4
4	carbon	epoxide resin on bisphenol A base, modified with polyurethane	2.4
5	carbon	epoxide resin on bisphenol A base, modified with polyurethane	1.5
6	carbon	epoxide resin on bisphenol A base	1.5
7	carbon	epoxide resin on bisphenol A base	2.2

1) Determined by IR spectroscopy after dissolution in methylene chloride at boiling temperature.

2) Components soluble in acetone at boiling temperature.

As a measure of stiffness of the fibre bundle (including finish) the square of the characteristic frequency of the torsion pendulum (TPT) and the resonance frequency of the vibrating system (DMA), respectively, was

selected. To reduce the influence of the fibre bundle dimensions, which can of course only be kept approximately constant, a relative stiffness was determined resulting from the quotient of the stiffness at the respective test temperature and the stiffness at 100 °C. This quotient served as a measure for the viscosity of the finish; it was recorded and evaluated in addition to the temperature dependent damping which was determined at the same time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Suitability of Thermomechanical Testing Methods for Characterisation of Fibre Finish

Figure 2 shows the relative stiffness and damping of materials tested within a temperature range from -100 °C to +360 °C. All materials tested show a stepped degradation of relative stiffness and a damping minimum related to it at temperatures below 60 °C (7). These are typical symptoms of a glass transition region. As glass transition regions of the fibres tested can be precluded within this temperature range they must be attributed to the finish. They are determined by the chemical structure and the mole mass of the finish.

At temperatures above 140 °C the stiffness of the fibre bundle increases again. This increase in stiffness is caused by chemical reaction (e.g. crosslinking) of the finish. If this chemical reaction starts below the glass transition temperature range of the chemically fully transformed finish (e.g. full crosslinking), a glass transition will occur during this reaction (1). This glass transition effects a contribution to the stiffness of the fibre bundle.

The temperature at the beginning of the chemical reaction, the stiffness change of the sample due to the chemical reaction, the occurrence of a glass transition during this reaction and its influence on the change of stiffness of the sample are dependent on material specific characteristics (e.g. reaction kinetic characteristics, change of glass transition temperature with increasing mole mass, etc.).

For the reasons specified above the thermomechanical testing methods applied have proved to be suitable for characterising finish on fibres.

Example for Characterisation

For the characterisation of the type of finish on the fibres tested the temperatures at the beginning and end of the glass transition (relative stiffness), at the damping maximum and at the beginning of the chemical reaction were determined (Tables 2 and 3).

Figure 2a. Relative stiffness (a: DMA; b: TPT), damping (c: DMA) and logarithmic decrement (d: TPT) of materials 1 to 3 as a function of temperature

Figure 2b. Relative stiffness (a: DMA; b: TPT), damping (c: DMA) and logarithmic decrement (d: TPT) of materials 4 to 7 as a function of temperature

TABLE 2

Characteristic data of the glass transitions of studied materials

Mat.	First Glass Transition (T), °C						Second Glass Transition, °C					
	Beginning ¹⁾		End ¹⁾		Damping Maximum		Beginning ¹⁾		End ¹⁾		Damping Maximum	
	TPT	DMA	TPT	DMA	TPT	DMA	TPT	DMA	TPT	DMA	TPT	DMA
1	50	40	61	61	51	53	-73	-75	-13	-56	--2)	--2)
2	0	-3	25	19	12	12	-79	-80	-61	-68	-77	-72
3	30	27	45	50	35	40	-80	-79	16	-58	--2)	-60
4	-22	-18	7	24	-5	5	--2)	--2)	--2)	--2)	--2)	--2)
5	-33	-38	-14	0	-17	-15	--2)	--2)	--2)	--2)	--2)	--2)
6	0	1	25	25	15	15	-75	-79	--2)	-61	--2)	-70
7	0	1	23	21	14	13	-83	-95	--2)	-64	--2)	--2)

1) Intersection of the tangents of adjacent inflection points and elong. straight lines of adjacent curve shapes, respectively.

2) Not identifiable.

TABLE 3

Characteristic data of the chemical reaction of studied materials

Mat.	First Increase of Stiffness, °C 1)		Second Increase of Stiffness, °C 1)	
	TPT	DMA	TPT	DMA
1	297	284	--2)	--2)
2	323	310	--2)	--2)
3	298	137	--2)	293
4	300	319	--2)	--2)
5	300	311	--2)	--2)
6	303	200	--2)	328
7	295	220	--2)	328

1) 2) See table 1

Glass Transition

The changes in stiffness and damping of the different types of finish often differ considerably at temperatures below 60 °C. Contrary to materials 4 and 5 the materials 1, 2, 3, 6 and 7 exhibit several glass transition regions. Whereas in the DMA all first and second glass transitions, respectively, are well defined, in the TPT the second glass transitions are often hard to identify. The decrease in relative stiffness after the beginning of the second glass transition often extends over a relatively large temperature region. Using this method determination of the end of this second glass transition is extremely difficult if possible at all.

If the values for the characterisation of the first glass transition from both methods are compared for the individual materials, the results normally will correspond. Only the temperatures at the end of the glass transition regions of materials 4 and 5 differ by more than 10 K.

The differences are presumably due to the specific stress conditions, especially in the $+45^\circ$ direction, and the less dense arrangement of the fibres with the TPT.

If the first glass transition temperature region is classified by type of finish (see Table 1) it is

- highest for polyvinyl acetate at approx. 30 to 60 °C (inclusive of beginning and end)
- markedly lower at 0 to 25 °C for epoxide resin on bisphenol A basis modified with ester, and
- lowest at -40 to 25 °C (DMA) and -30 to 5 °C (TPT) for epoxide resin on bisphenol A basis modified with polyurethane (7).

In contrast to the two epoxide base finishes without modifier those on a polyvinyl acetate base and epoxide resin modified with polyurethane having similar chemical composition exhibit different glass transition regions. This is probably due to a different mole mass (degree of cross-linking) and/or a different mole mass distribution or other IR spectroscopically unidentifiable material differences.

Chemical Reaction

Especially at temperatures above 140 °C the changes in the relative stiffness of the different types of finish often differ considerably. Materials 1, 2, 4 and 5 e.g. show a single step increase in relative stiffness during the DMA. In contrast, materials 3, 6 and 7 exhibit a stiffness

increase of several steps, the first step being relatively small. This multi-stepped stiffness increase cannot be detected by the TPT.

If the temperatures at the beginning of the first stiffness increase (Table 3) from both methods are compared for the different types of finish, often considerable differences can be found. The values for those materials showing only a single step stiffness increase are generally lower with the TPT. For the other materials a reverse tendency can be observed. These differences are attributed to procedure-specific conditions (different load conditions, different environment medium).

In addition, the temperatures at the beginning of the first stiffness increase of finish types showing a two step stiffness increase are substantially lower than the temperatures of finish types with a single step stiffness increase. Allocation of these temperatures to the chemical structure of the main components of the finish is much more difficult to achieve than at the glass transitions in the low-molecular state. One of the possible causes of this could be the influence of the surface of the different fibres tested on the chemical reaction of the finish.

CONCLUSIONS

It was possible to characterise all tested types of finish on ready-for-processing fibres by means of the torsion pendulum test and the dynamic-mechanic analysis. As criteria for the characterisation of the finish glass transitions and chemical reactions were used. The test results revealed that these characteristic features can appear at highly varying temperature regions on different types of finish. Thus, the test methods used permit establishment of thermomechanical "finger-prints" for finish types on fibres, which can be a great advantage for the quality assurance of this important component of fibre composites.

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